

Luminex Assay: ProcartaPlex High Sensitivity Kits (mouse)

Time: Day 1 (2hrs) + Day 2 (4hrs + plate read) *times may vary for first-time users. To save time, label tubes for standards, predilute tissue to 5mg/ml (store at -80°C), and design plate/batch on the luminex software before Day 1.*

Before you begin: For use with mouse tissue post-homogenization (ex. brain, not serum) and protein assay diluted to appropriate working concentration (brain – 5mg/ml protein) in BioRad Cell Lysis Buffer.

DAY 1 (2hrs)

Make sure all kits (buffer and beads/antibody) are at room temperature for 20 mins before beginning.

Stage 1: Prepare Reagents (thaw tissue at same time)

Wash Buffer (50x → 1x) 250ml per 96-well plate

- Vortex the Wash Buffer (50x) for 15 seconds. In a 250ml glass screw top jar combine **25ml** Wash Buffer (50x) with **225ml** ddH₂O (in the purple-lidded carboy by the washing sink).
- Wash Buffer (1x) can be stored at 4°C for up to 6 months.

Bead Solution (1x) 5ml containing 50µl of each bead per 96-well plate – LIGHT SENSITIVE

- This solution made in Wash Buffer (1x) will contain 50µl from each stock High Sensitivity Bead vial (brown vial, 50x). Make in the 10ml flat-bottom conical with teal screw top cap.
- Vortex each vial of beads (brown vial, 50x) for 30 seconds and add **50µl** of each to a vial of Wash Buffer (1x) so that the total volume of all beads + wash buffer is **5ml**.

# of different bead vials	volume of beads (50x)	volume of wash buffer (1x)
1	50µl	4950µl
2	50µl each	4900µl
3	50µl each	4850µl

- Store Bead Solution in the dark at room temperature until use.

Standards (5x → 1x) 250µl final volume per 96-well plate

- Each bead/antibody kit will have its own standard (clear vial with blue cap). **MAKE SURE THAT NO ANALYTE IS ON MORE THAN ONE STANDARD** from each kit you are using. As long as there is no overlap of analytes you are quantifying between standards, you may combine standards from multiple kits to ensure that each of your analytes can be measured. Note: the standard from one kit may contain multiple analytes; in that case only use the standard from one kit. In general, use the minimum number of standard vials to detect all desired analytes.
- Take one standard vial per kit (each kit comes with 2 identical vials) and spin for 10 seconds.
- Add **50µl** of BioRad Cell Lysis Buffer to each vial of standards.
- Vortex each vial for 10 seconds and spin for 10 seconds.

- Put vials at 4°C for **5-10 mins**.
- If using only 1 standard: add 200µl of BioRad Cell Lysis Buffer.
 - If combining more than one standard: combine **50µl** of each standard in a 500µl tube and bring up to **250µl total volume** with BioRad Cell Lysis Buffer.

# of standards	volume per vial	buffer to add	total volume
1	50µl	200µl	250µl
2	50µl each	150µl	250µl
3	50µl each	100µl	250µl

- *If using more than 5 standards call the manufacturer for help.*
- Vortex and spin the combined standard solution for 10 seconds.

Standard Dilutions (n=8, 4-fold dilutions) 150µl of each per 96-well plate

- Make in 500µl tubes. Vortex and spin each tube as you go.

	volume of standard	volume of BioRad Cell Lysis Buffer	Total Volume
Standard 1	20µl of combined standard solution	180µl	200µl
Standard 2	50µl of Std 1	150µl	200µl
Standard 3	50µl of Std 2	150µl	200µl
Standard 4	50µl of Std 3	150µl	200µl
Standard 5	50µl of Std 4	150µl	200µl
Standard 6	50µl of Std 5	150µl	200µl
Standard 7	50µl of Std 6	150µl	200µl
Standard 8	50µl of Std 7	150µl	200µl
Blank	none	150µl	150µl

Stage 2: Procedure

Note: if same solution is being added to all wells use the multi-channel pipet.

Add Magnetic Beads to 96-well plate

- Remove Bead Solution from storage in dark, vortex for 30 seconds, and add **50µl** of solution to each well.
- Put plate on magnet and let sit for **2 minutes**.
- **Wash Procedure:** While on magnet, dump liquid in sink then invert plate on paper towels and allow excess liquid to absorb. Tap the plate on adjacent section of paper towel to remove any residual liquid. Add **150µl** of Wash Buffer (1x) to each well, wait **30 seconds**, then dump liquid into sink. Repeat 2x.
- Remove plate from magnet.

Add Standards & Samples to plate

- Add **25µl** of Universal Assay Buffer (1x) to each well
- Using your plate map: add **25µl** of blanks, standards, or samples to dedicated wells
- Seal the plate and cover with black lid. Place in 4°C on shaker and **incubate overnight**.

DAY 2 (4hrs + plate read)

Make sure all kits (buffer and beads/antibody) are at room temperature for 20 mins before beginning.

Stage 1: Prepare Reagents

Detection Antibodies (50x → 1x) 3ml per 96-well plate

- Vortex briefly each detection antibody vial (purple cap). In a 5ml tube combine **35µl** of each antibody (50x) and bring up to final volume of **3ml** with detection antibody diluent.

# of antibodies	volume of antibody	volume of diluent
1	35µl	2965µl
2	35µl each	2930µl
3	35µl each	2895µl

Stage 2: Procedure

*Wash liquid off wells on magnet (see **Wash Procedure** above)*

Add detection antibodies

- Add **25µl** of detection antibodies to each well
- Seal the plate and remove from magnet. Tap plate into side of free hand to spread contents across well bottom. Cover with black lid and put on shaker at room temperature for **45 minutes**.

*Wash liquid off wells on magnet (see **Wash Procedure** above)*

Add Streptavidin-PE

- Add **50µl** of SAPE (light sensitive) to each well
- Seal the plate and remove from magnet. Tap plate into side of free hand to spread contents across well bottom. Cover with black lid and put on shaker at room temperature for **30 minutes**.

*Wash liquid off wells on magnet (see **Wash Procedure** above)*

Amplification

- Add **50µl** of Amplification Reagent 1 to each well
- Seal the plate and remove from magnet. Tap plate into side of free hand to spread contents across well bottom. Cover with black lid and put on shaker at room temperature for **30 minutes**.
- DO NOT WASH
- Add **50µl** of Amplification Reagent 2 to each well

- Seal the plate and remove from magnet. Tap plate into side of free hand to spread contents across well bottom. Cover with black lid and put on shaker at room temperature for **30 minutes**.

*Wash liquid off wells on magnet (see **Wash Procedure** above)*

Add Reading Buffer

- Remove from magnet and add **120µl** of Reading Buffer to the center of each well. Expel the liquid straight on with force to stir up/agitate contents of well.
- Seal the plate and cover with black lid. Put on shaker at room temperature for **5 minutes**.
- Remove plate seal and plate is ready to run on Luminex machine.

PROCEDURE SUMMARY

DAY 1 (2 hours)

- ❖ Prepare wash buffer, bead solution, and standards
- ❖ Add 50µl of beads → wash
- ❖ Add 25µl of UAB + 25µl of blank, standards, samples → incubate overnight at 4°C

DAY 2 (4 hours + plate read)

- ❖ Prepare detection antibodies
- ❖ Wash → add 25µl detection antibodies for 45 minutes
- ❖ Wash → add 50µl SAPE for 30 minutes
- ❖ Wash → add 50µl Amplification Reagent 1 for 30 minutes
- ❖ DO NOT WASH → add 50µl Amplification Reagent 2 for 30 minutes
- ❖ Wash → add 120µl of Reading Buffer for 5 minutes
- ❖ Read in luminex machine (~1hr per plate)